

Brithys crini pancratia

Lily borer

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© J van Wyk

Group: Insect

Size: About 40 mm long, with a wingspan of roughly 40 mm.

Distribution:

It has a wide, primarily paleotropical and subtropical distribution, largely determined by the presence of its host plants in the Amaryllidaceae family.

Importance:

It is an indigenous insect adapted to feeding on local deciduous species, forming a natural part of the ecosystem. By damaging the rhizome's main growth point, its larvae trigger the plant to produce multiple smaller offsets, leading to clumping.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 40.81 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 7.92 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.56 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.0% [Single: 96.0%, Duplicated: 3.1%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 15 758.47 kilobases

Contig number: 2 502

Sample Contributor contact details:

Joubert van Wyk

Clivia Society

jjwyk@iafrica.com

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